

Species-habitat networks inform pollinator conservation strategies in cities

Costanza Geppert^{a,*}, Andree Cappellari^a, Maurizio Mei^b, Dino Paniccia^c, Lorenzo Marini^a

^a Department of Agronomy, Food, Natural Resources, Animals and Environment (DAFNAE), University of Padova, Legnaro, PD, Italy

^b Department of Biology and Biotechnology "Charles Darwin", Sapienza University of Rome, Piazzale Aldo Moro 5, 00185, Rome, Italy

^c Via Colle 13, 03100, Frosinone, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ecological networks
Urban greening
Bees
Hoverflies
Management
City

ABSTRACT

As more people live in cities, research on the ecological role of urban green for pollinators is accumulating. However, most studies have focused on the diversity patterns at the local scale, while an urgent question is to understand how to manage whole cities to maximise pollinator conservation.

Here, we selected 105 sites belonging to 6 habitat types (abandoned meadows, crop field margins, gardens, parks, parks managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime, and road margins) in the city of Padua (Italy). We sampled bees and hoverflies using transect walks, from spring to late summer, and analysed species-habitat networks to understand how pollinator communities were organized across urban green areas.

We found that most pollinator species interacted with most habitat types in the city, creating a highly generalistic and robust network. Compared to all other habitats, road margins had a very small influence over the network and hosted the lowest pollinator abundance and species richness. Green areas in the landscape positively affected wild bees but local patch quality, in terms of flowers and low mowing regime, was key. Network robustness decreased when the patches with the highest quality were removed first, and pollinators depended on the patches with the highest flower cover and vegetation height.

Except for road margins, all habitat patches could support pollinator species. Therefore, urban planning strategies could be tailored without considering habitat identity, for example by increasing the overall amount of green areas and by implementing management practices that enhance the floral resources across all urban green spaces.

1. Introduction

Urbanization is increasing worldwide, posing a major threat to biodiversity (Li et al., 2022; Liang et al., 2023). Concerning pollinator insects, research on the effect of urbanization has been quickly accumulating over the last decade, showing contrasting results (Remmers and Frantzeskaki, 2024). While arthropod diversity mostly decreases with increasing cemented cover (Fenoglio et al., 2020; Theodorou et al., 2020), cities can host a high abundance of pollinators, especially species adapted to high human disturbance (Casanelles-Abella et al., 2022; Fournier et al., 2020; Geppert et al., 2022; McCune et al., 2023; Rivest and Kharouba, 2024). As pollinator insects are declining and human density in cities is predicted to increase, it is important to understand how we should guide urban planning to support pollinators in cities.

Fundamental drivers of urban pollinator communities are the quality, quantity and spatial arrangement of urban green areas. Urban habitat types are many and may differ in their management and in the

amount of floral and nesting resources (Baldock et al., 2019). Private gardens, for example, are usually highly rewarding in terms of flowers but the unregulated use of herbicides, insecticides and fungicides may negatively impact pollinators (Baldock et al., 2019; Daniels et al., 2020; Muratet and Fontaine, 2015). By contrast, public parks can offer larger, pesticide-free areas and nest sites (McFrederick and LeBuhn, 2006). Road margins are also very common in cities but they are expected to be exposed to multiple impacts such as fragmentation, frequent mowing and pollution (Phillips et al., 2020). Understanding the role of different habitat types in supporting pollinator communities is key to informing urban planning for pollinator conservation. Usually, a high abundance and diversity of floral resources in urban environments leads to an increase in pollinator diversity (Banaszak-Cibicka et al., 2018; Lanner et al., 2020; Wilson and Jamieson, 2019). Therefore, interventions in green areas, such as decreasing mowing regime, can help promote pollinators (Biella et al., 2025; Cloutier et al., 2024; Proske et al., 2022; Süle et al., 2023). Even if research on urban pollinators has quickly

* Corresponding author at: University of Padova, Viale dell'Università 16, 35020, Legnaro, PD, Italy.

E-mail address: costanza.geppert@unipd.it (C. Geppert).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111680>

Received 8 October 2025; Received in revised form 2 December 2025; Accepted 19 December 2025

Available online 5 January 2026

0006-3207/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

accumulated over the last decade, studies have mostly focused on diversity patterns at the local scale, comparing pollinator species richness between different habitat types (Baldock et al., 2015; Dylewski et al., 2019; Tonietto et al., 2011), while an urgent question is to understand how to manage whole cities to maximise pollinator conservation. For example, one key practical question is whether habitat type or habitat quality matters the most.

Green areas in cities form a network of potentially suitable habitats for pollinators embedded in an inhospitable matrix dominated by cemented surfaces. In this context, pollinator species and habitat patches can be represented as nodes in a bipartite species-habitat network (Marini et al., 2019). Species-habitat networks can be used to reveal the complex architecture of associations between multiple habitats and entire communities of pollinators across heterogeneous landscapes. First, topological metrics such as connectance and modularity can describe how pollinator communities are organized across the whole network of urban green areas (Lami et al., 2021). In particular, large modularity and low connectance would indicate that urban pollinators tend to form strong associations with certain habitat types or groups of patches, suggesting the need to manage and protect single modules to maintain diversity at the whole city level. Second, network robustness can be used to measure the effect of losing green areas on the stability of pollinator communities at the scale of the whole city. Finally, species-habitat networks allow to identify single habitat patches of particular importance in supporting the highest number of pollinators or rare specialists at the city level (Cappellari and Marini, 2021). This approach can expand the existing studies on the local effect of urban habitat types, providing key information to design conservation strategies at the

landscape scale (Dong et al., 2025).

Here, we studied how bees and hoverflies use green patches in the city of Padua, with the overall goal to provide effective strategies to build pollinator friendly cities. We sampled 105 sites belonging to six habitat types (i.e. abandoned meadows, crop field margins, gardens, conventionally managed parks, parks managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime, and road margins), from spring to late summer. The sampling covered the whole city and allowed us to describe the general structure of the species-habitat network and to identify the habitat dependencies. In particular, we hypothesized that: i) pollinator communities would be associated (forming modules) with specific habitat types, such as abandoned meadows and gardens; ii) the network would be robust to the random loss of habitat patches; iii) the pollinator community would benefit from increasing green areas at the landscape scale.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area and sampling design

The study area was the city of Padua, Italy (Fig. 1a). Padua's population is estimated at 209,802, in 2022 (Comune di Padova - Elaborazione del Settore Programmazione Controllo e Statistica su dati dell'Anagrafe). The climate is temperate: from 2000 to 2022, the mean annual temperature was 14.5 °C, min annual temperature was 10.6 °C, max annual temperature was 19.2 °C, and mean annual precipitation was 913 mm (<https://www.arpa.veneto.it/dati-ambientali/open-data>). In the city, we selected 15 landscapes, consisting of circles with a 750 m

Fig. 1. Study area in the city of Padua, Italy (a); the 105 sampling sites belonging to different habitat types (b); and the pollinator habitat network of the whole city collapsed to the six nodes representing the six habitat types (c). The colours of the habitat patches in the map (b) are the same of the network (c). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

diameter and a mean distance between the centroids = $5.35 \text{ km} \pm 2.32$. Landscapes were selected to homogeneously cover the whole city. Within each landscape, we chose 7 sampling sites, for a total of $7 \times 15 = 105$ patches. The mean distance among patches within the same landscape was $695 \text{ m} \pm 86 \text{ SD}$ (Fig. 1b). To quantify the overall amount of green area in each landscape, we used Google Earth Pro 7.3.4.8642 and manually drew polygons representing all types of green areas. We placed sampling sites in all green habitat types that are common in the city of Padua and suitable for pollinator insects.

2.2. Habitat types

We considered the following six habitat types: abandoned meadows, crop field margins, gardens, conventionally managed parks, parks managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime and road margins (see pictures and detailed description of the habitat types in Fig. S1). The habitat types differed in terms of management, ranging from abandoned meadows that were completely unmanaged to road margins that were frequently mowed, i.e. approximately every two weeks (Fig. S1). Parks in the city were regularly mowed every two/three weeks during the growing season, for a total of around 10 mowing events. However, within each landscape, one park was selected and managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime with the help of Padua's municipality. The pollinator friendly mowing regime consisted of delimiting an area of 20 m^2 that was mowed two times, once in April and once in August. Reduced frequency of mowing regime is often proposed as a strategy to help pollinators (Berger et al., 2024; Proske et al., 2022). Overall, in each landscape, we selected one patch per habitat type, except for road margins, for which we selected two patches to reflect their high abundance in the city; in two landscapes, sampling included two gardens and one road margin.

2.3. Patch quality (management and floral resources)

At each patch, we delimited a transect of $10 \text{ m} \times 2 \text{ m}$ in a sunny, dry area, avoiding humid spots and edges, such as hedgerows. To characterize the quality of the patch, we considered the management and the available floral resources. We quantified the overall herbaceous vegetation height along the transect, identified all flowering plant species and assessed their relative abundance. Herbaceous height is a proxy for mowing frequency, a key management aspect, while flowering plant species richness and flower cover represent the abundance and diversity of locally available food resources for pollinators. The sampling was repeated four times, once per month, between May and August 2022. At each patch, we calculated flowering plant species α -diversity, mean flower cover and mean herbaceous vegetation height. By analysing the effect of the habitat type on herbaceous vegetation height, flowering plant species richness and flower cover, we confirmed high heterogeneity and significant differences among the selected habitat types (Fig. S2, Table S1). Abandoned meadows and parks managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime had the highest herbaceous vegetation height, suggesting either a lack of management or an extensive management regime. Abandoned meadows, gardens and parks managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime showed the highest richness in flowering plant species. Moreover, abandoned meadows had the highest flower cover and road margins the lowest. Therefore, the selected habitat types differed from one another but did not consistently indicate good or poor quality for pollinators, except for abandoned meadows and road margins maintaining good and poor conditions, respectively.

2.4. Pollinator sampling

Each habitat patch was sampled four times: one round was carried out during the first ten days of May 2022, one during the first ten days of June 2022, one during the first two weeks of July 2022 and the last during the second week of August 2022. At each patch, pollinator

insects, i.e. bees and hoverflies, were sampled for 20 min along the transect ($10 \text{ m} \times 2 \text{ m}$). We considered bees and hoverflies because they are the most common and abundant pollinator groups in the study area. Whenever possible, we identified pollinators in the field (i.e. specimens belonging to the species *Apis mellifera* Linnaeus, 1758, *Halictus scabiosae* (Rossi, 1790), *Bombus pascuorum* (Scopoli, 1763) and *Bombus terrestris* Linnaeus, 1758); otherwise, we placed them in vials with 70 % ethanol. When pollinators were morphologically similar and could not all be captured, a subsample was collected for identification, and the remainder was counted rather than collected. Surveys were carried out between 9 a.m. and 6 p.m. in weather conditions allowing the activity of the studied insects (sunny or partly cloudy and temperature above $15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Collected specimens were brought to the laboratory and were identified by experts (AC and MM identified bees, while DP identified hoverflies) to the species level.

2.5. Statistical analysis

2.5.1. Pollinator habitat patch networks

We built pollinator-habitat patch networks from adjacency matrices A_{ij} in which i refers to the visited patch, j the pollinator species, and ij pollinator abundance (Fig. 1c). We built one bipartite weighted pollinator-habitat patch network, using quantitative (weighted) networks because they are considered more robust and precise than binary networks (Blüthgen et al., 2006; Dormann and Strauss, 2014). We calculated four network-level metrics providing non-redundant information: connectance, weighted specialisation (H^2), modularity and robustness to the loss of habitat patches. Connectance is a measure of network complexity, i.e. the realized proportion of all possible links in a network, ranging between 0 (simple network) and 1 (complex network) (Dunne et al., 2002). We calculated modularity, defined as the tendency to form modules in which species and habitat patches are linked more strongly with each other than with the rest of the network (Olesen et al., 2007). As a tool for the quantification of modularity, we opted for the DIRTLPawb + algorithm (Beckett, 2016). After running the modularity algorithm, we identified the modules and attributed each patch to its habitat according to the a priori classification. To quantify the agreement between habitat identity and modules, we used the agreement metric and the procedure described in (Lami et al., 2021). The approach tests whether patches belonging to the same habitat tend to form modules. Third, we estimated the weighted specialisation index H^2 . This metric is an estimate for the network-wide degree of specificity, and it ranges from 0 (=no specificity) to 1 (=maximum specificity). For connectance, modularity and H^2 , we then checked for metric significance using z-scores, calculated using 500 null models obtained with the Patefield algorithm (Dormann and Strauss, 2014). Finally, we calculated network robustness, i.e. a measure of network stability against node removal. To calculate robustness to habitat loss, we removed habitat patches following four scenarios: random removal of patches, removal of patches from the richest in flowering plant species to the poorest, removal of patches from the ones with the highest flower cover to the ones with the lowest flower cover, and removal of patches from the ones with the highest herbaceous vegetation to the lowest. Robustness ranges between 0 (highly unstable network) and 1 (highly stable network) (Memmott et al., 2004). To compare observed robustness with the null expectations, we created 1000 random networks keeping connectance, number of patches and species richness constant and compared the observed robustness to the random distribution using z-scores. We used the Vaznull algorithm because this null model keeps connectance constant, which in turn strongly affects robustness (Dunne et al., 2004). To compute network-level metrics, we used the bipartite package (Dormann et al., 2008a).

Following the same approach described above, we generated the same network metrics but this time collapsing all patches belonging to the same habitat type, resulting in a network with six nodes only.

At the node level, we measured the strength of each habitat patch

using the strength() function in bipartite (Dormann et al., 2008b). Strength is the sum of all the dependencies of all pollinators on a specific patch. Mathematically, the dependency D_{ij} of a pollinator species j on a patch i can be defined as:

$$D_{ij} = \frac{A_{ij}}{\sum_k A_{kj}}$$

where A_{ij} is the abundance of the pollinator species j in the patch i and $\sum_k A_{kj}$ is the sum of the abundances of pollinator species j in all patches in the network. A higher dependency value means that species j relies more heavily on patch i compared to other patches in the network, which can indicate a more specialized relationship. Hence, patch strength quantifies how strongly the species are dependent on that patch. Since strength depends on the number of pollinator species in each patch, we divided it by species richness.

2.5.2. The effect of habitat type, percentage of green areas and patch quality on node metrics

First, we pooled all sampling rounds and computed the species abundance and richness at the patch level, for bees and hoverflies separately. To test the effect of habitat type, green area in the landscape and patch quality on node level metrics at the patch level, we used linear mixed models fitted with the R package *nlme* (Pinheiro et al., 2017). We tested the response of patch strength, bee species richness, bee abundance, hoverfly species richness and hoverfly abundance with two linear mixed models: (i) using as fixed factors habitat type (abandoned meadows, crop field margins, gardens, conventionally managed parks, pollinator friendly managed parks, and road margins), and percentage of green area in the landscape; and (ii) using as fixed factors mean flower cover across all rounds, and mean herbaceous vegetation height across all rounds. We could not test the effect of habitat type, mean flower cover and mean herbaceous vegetation height in the same model because of collinearity with habitat type (Table S1). Using the *vif* function of the package *car* (Fox et al., 2012), we checked for potential collinearity between mean flower cover and mean vegetation height. Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) values were close to 1 for all fitted models, showing no collinearity (Akinwande et al., 2015). In both models, we used a natural logarithmic transformation of all response variables to meet the assumption of normally distributed residuals, and, to take into account spatial dependence in our sampling, we included landscape ID as random factor. Residuals were visually checked using the R package *car*. We fitted the same models assuming negative binomial distributions but linear mixed-effects model performed better. All analyses were performed using R 4.3.0 (R Core Team, 2017).

3. Results

3.1. General results

Overall, we captured 4498 bee individuals belonging to 128 species and 721 hoverflies belonging to 37 species (Tables S2 and S3). The most abundant bee species were *Apis mellifera* ($n = 1514$), *Halictus scabiosae* ($n = 397$), and *Bombus pascuorum* ($n = 370$), while the most abundant hoverfly species were *Sphaerophoria scripta* Linnaeus, 1758 ($n = 214$), *Episyrphus balteatus* (De Geer, 1776) ($n = 164$), and *Melanostoma mellinum* Linnaeus, 1758 ($n = 73$).

3.2. Species-habitat patch network

The species-habitat network ($N = 105$ patches) showed low connectance (connectance = 0.091) (Table S4). Connectance was lower than expected from null models (z -score = -45.2), similarly to ecological interaction networks. By contrast, modularity (modularity = 0.320) was higher than expected from null models (z -score = 90.6). However, we observed a small agreement between modules and habitat identity

(mean $A = 0.32$, SD = 0.14) and the values were similar to those expected using the null model, i.e. there was a large overlap between the null and the observed density distribution ($\eta = 0.86$, SD = 0.04). This means that the modules did not correspond to the habitat type. Specialisation was also low ($H^2 = 0.302$), even though its value was higher than expected from the null models (z -score = 102.709). The network showed a relatively stable structure to the random loss of habitat patches (observed robustness = 0.741) but the network was significantly less robust than expected by chance (z -score = -2.454 from Vaznull models). The loss of 80 % of random patches was required to achieve a loss of 50 % of the pollinator species. The observed robustness calculated by removing patches starting from the ones with the highest percentage of green areas was 0.710, starting from the ones with the highest flower cover was 0.590, starting from the ones with the highest vegetation height was 0.630, and starting from the ones richest in flowering plant species was 0.648 (Fig. 2).

3.3. Importance of different habitat types and percentage of green areas in the landscape

Standardized patch strength, i.e. the degree to which the pollinator species depend on the patch, was marginally affected by habitat type (Table S5). The only significant difference was the higher patch strength of abandoned meadows compared to road margins. Patch strength was not affected by the percentage of green areas. Bee abundance and species richness responded to habitat type and to the percentage of green areas (Table S5). Compared to the abandoned meadows, bee abundance was lower in crop field margins, road margins, and parks managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime, while no significant differences were found for gardens and conventionally mowed parks (Fig. 3a and b). Similarly, bee species richness was reduced in crop field margins and road margins compared to abandoned meadows, with marginally non-significant decreases in gardens and parks. Moreover, hoverfly abundance and species richness were the lowest in road margins, and no other habitat type differed substantially from abandoned meadows (Fig. 3c and d, Table S5). Increasing the amount of green areas in the landscape increased the abundance and species richness of bees, while it did not have a significant effect on hoverflies (Fig. 4a and b).

Fig. 2. Empirical extinction curves obtained through 1000 randomizations of sequential removal of sites on the pollinator species pool at the whole city level. Removal of sites was random (blue), from the sites with the highest percentage of green areas in the landscape to the lowest (grey), from the sites with the highest flower cover to the lowest (red), from the sites with the highest vegetation height to the lowest (green), from the sites with the flowering plant species richness to the lowest (pink). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Effects of the habitat type on the natural logarithmic transformed abundance and species richness of bees (a, b) and hoverflies (c, d). (ab = abandoned meadows, fm = crop field margins, ga = gardens, pa = conventionally managed parks, rm = road margins, and sp = parks managed with a pollinator friendly mowing regime). Different letters (a, b) indicate significant differences among groups based on a post hoc Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 4. Effects of the percentage of green areas in the landscape (within a 750-m radius) on (a) bee abundance and (b) bee species richness, shown on a natural-logarithmic scale. The line shows model-predicted marginal effects, with 95 % confidence intervals from the linear mixed-effects model. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.4. Importance of patch quality

Patch strength increased with increasing mean flower cover and increasing herbaceous vegetation height (Fig. 5, Table S6). Bee abundance, bee species richness, hoverfly abundance, and hoverfly species richness increased with increasing flower cover (Table S6). By contrast, only bee species richness was positively affected by mean herbaceous vegetation height, whereas herbaceous vegetation height did not significantly affect bee abundance or hoverflies.

Fig. 5. Effects of mean flower cover (a) and mean herbaceous vegetation height (b) on patch strength transformed with the natural logarithm. As strength mathematically depends on the number of pollinator species occurring in each patch, we divided its value by species richness (S). The line shows model-predicted marginal effects, with 95 % confidence intervals from the linear mixed-effects model.

4. Discussion

Our study attempts to understand how to manage urban green areas for pollinator conservation at the whole city level. We showed that pollinator communities tended to be weakly associated with specific habitat types. Most pollinator species interacted with most habitat types in the city, creating a generalistic network in terms of habitat preference. However, pollinators depended more strongly on the patches with the highest flower cover and less disturbed herbaceous vegetation. As a result, the urban pollinator communities were highly robust against patch loss when the removal was random, but less robust when the patches with the highest floral resources and vegetation height were removed first.

The species-habitat network offered insights into how bees and hoverflies use urban green areas at the whole city level. The network was weakly modular and weakly connected, indicating the existence of ecological constraints or dispersal limitation that reduce the number of realized links across urban landscapes. Despite the low connectance, the species-habitat network was generally robust against the random loss of habitat patches. This contrasts with the current understanding of the often observed positive relationship between connectance and robustness (Dunne et al., 2002). Our simulations indicated that the random loss of 50 % of the habitat patches led only to the loss of approximately 20 % of the species at the whole city level. Due to specific conditions linked to anthropic disturbance, urban landscapes probably act as strong environmental filters (Gathof et al., 2022), selecting a subset of well-adapted pollinators that are likely able to exploit most urban resources irrespective of the habitat type (Baldock et al., 2015; Buchholz and Egerer, 2020; Casanelles-Abella et al., 2022; Ferrari and Polidori, 2022; Fournier et al., 2020; Geppert et al., 2022; McCune et al., 2023; Remmers and Frantzeskaki, 2024). Our results confirmed this, as both the level of network specialisation and the lack of agreement among modules and habitat types suggested that most pollinator species tended to visit all habitat types without any preference. This is even more evident when all the patches belonging to the same habitat were collapsed into a single node. In this network, all species occurred in all habitats. However, when habitat patches were removed starting with the patches with the highest flower cover, vegetation height or richness in flowering plant species, network robustness decreased. The loss of 50 % of the habitat patches with the highest flower cover led to the loss of approximately 40 % of the pollinator species. This suggests that, more than the habitat type, it is the patch quality and, therefore, also the management that affects the role of each patch in the pollinator network.

We found that the influence of each node on the whole network changed only slightly depending on the habitat type. No habitat patch hosted a subset of species exhibiting a strong preference for that specific habitat type, and the only significant effect was due to the very low

patch strength of road margins. Therefore, all habitat types supported similar pollinator species across the whole network, except for road margins. Similarly, the species richness of bees and hoverflies was slightly affected by habitat type, with similar levels of pollinator abundance and species richness across habitats, except for road margins. Road margins were the least suitable for pollinator insects, showing the lowest patch strength and abundance and diversity of pollinators. This is probably due to the combination of small size, low floral resources and high frequency of disturbance and pollution. Road margins were frequently mowed, exposed to diverse forms of pollution, including light, noise, exhaust fumes and heavy metals, and roads might be a partial or complete barrier to movement for pollinators (Dargas et al., 2016; Ferrari et al., 2024; Girling et al., 2013; Greenleaf et al., 2007; Phillips et al., 2020). Especially given the significant area that they collectively cover, we join other studies in calling for future studies on the effect of changing management approaches in road margins (Baldock et al., 2019; Brown et al., 2024; Meinzen et al., 2024; Phillips et al., 2020). However, the potential risks connected to the proximity to roads, including direct mortality and pollution exposure, should be considered too. Finally, the abundance and diversity of bees increased with an increase in the overall green areas. This result is in accordance with previous studies that found that the percentage of cemented cover and the fragmentation of green areas affect pollinator communities, for example by reducing ground nesting bee species as well as large-bodied and specialist bees (Buchholz et al., 2020; Ferrari and Polidori, 2022; Pereira et al., 2021).

Patch strength, bee diversity and abundance and hoverfly abundance were affected by the patch quality, i.e. flower cover and vegetation height. Pollinators were dependent on the patches with high floral resources and high herbaceous vegetation. Moreover, increasing flower resources or vegetation height usually led to higher abundance and diversity of both bees and hoverflies. These results support the accumulating evidence on the positive effect of some management practices on pollinators in urban environments, such as decreasing mowing frequency or planting flowering species (Halbritter et al., 2015; Hemmings et al., 2022; Jakobsson et al., 2018; Lerman et al., 2018; Noordijk et al., 2009; Proske et al., 2022; Süle et al., 2023; Valtonen et al., 2006). The strong effect of floral resources is not surprising because of the well-known key role of flowers for pollinators in urban and non-urban environments. However, the lack of a strong habitat effect is inconsistent with previous findings, which often reported positive effects of local habitats, such as gardens or parks (Baldock et al., 2019; Daniels et al., 2020; Threlfall et al., 2015; Tonietto et al., 2011).

4.1. Management recommendations

From an urban planning perspective, there was no indication of particular habitat types that were key in the network and, thus, deserved higher priority for pollinator conservation. Regardless of the habitat type, the higher the overall amount of green areas in the landscape, the higher the local abundance and diversity of wild bees. All urban green areas, except for road margins, provided suitable habitats for pollinators. In particular, abandoned meadows maintained high local pollinator diversity, but their current role in green urban planning is often marginalized. Moreover, because of the overall large extension of road margins, management practices should be revised to better support pollinator populations, for example by reducing the frequency of mowing. What determined a patch to become a crucial player was the vegetation height, the flowering plant diversity, and the amount of floral resources offered. Therefore, the local management of urban green areas might be the main driver of pollinator communities, e.g. increasing flower resources (Felderhoff et al., 2023; Schwartz et al., 2013), and benefits can be achieved in all habitat types (Remmers and Frantzeskaki, 2024). Overall, our results highlight the importance of local pollinator management and suggest that urban environments can host a higher number of species and individuals of pollinators if the amount

of floral resources is increased and the anthropogenic disturbance, such as mowing, is decreased. These changes in management practices would result most likely in an increase in the abundance of the already occurring species but, as most of the urban species are generalistic, the pollinator friendly management of cities cannot replace the urgent need to protect semi-natural habitats, that host the rarest and most vulnerable pollinators (Remmers and Frantzeskaki, 2024).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Costanza Geppert: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Andree Cappellari:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Maurizio Mei:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Dino Panizza:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Lorenzo Marini:** Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

The research was partially supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 project “Safeguard” (Grant agreement ID: 101003476) funded under Societal Challenges - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials. This study was partly carried out within the Agritech National Research Center funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU, Mission 4 Component 2 CUP C93C22002790001. We are grateful to all the garden owners that participated in the study, G. P., L.A. and C.B. for their help during fieldwork.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111680>.

Data availability

Data are now available at: [10.5281/zenodo.18059923](https://zenodo.org/record/18059923).

References

- Akinwande, M.O., Dikko, H.G., Samson, A., 2015. Variance inflation factor: a condition for the inclusion of suppressor variable(s) in regression analysis. *Open J. Stat.* 05 (07), 754–767. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojs.2015.57075>.
- Baldock, K.C.R., Goddard, M.A., Hicks, D.M., Kunin, W.E., Mitschunas, N., Osgathorpe, L.M., Potts, S.G., Robertson, K.M., Scott, A.V., Stone, G.N., Vaughan, I.P., Memmott, J., 2015. Where is the UK's pollinator biodiversity? The importance of urban areas for flower-visiting insects. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 282 (1803), 20142849. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2014.2849>.
- Baldock, K.C.R., Goddard, M.A., Hicks, D.M., Kunin, W.E., Mitschunas, N., Morse, H., Osgathorpe, L.M., Potts, S.G., Robertson, K.M., Scott, A.V., Staniczenko, P.P.A., Stone, G.N., Vaughan, I.P., Memmott, J., 2019. A systems approach reveals urban pollinator hotspots and conservation opportunities. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 3 (3), 363–373. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-018-0769-y>.
- Banaszak-Cibicka, W., Twerd, L., Fliszkiewicz, M., Giejdasz, K., Langowska, A., 2018. City parks vs. natural areas—is it possible to preserve a natural level of bee richness and abundance in a city park? *Urban Ecosyst.* 21 (4), 599–613. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-018-0756-8>.
- Beckett, S.J., 2016. Improved community detection in weighted bipartite networks. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* 3 (1), 140536. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.140536>.
- Berger, J.L., Daum, S.N.K., Hartlieb, M., 2024. Simply the green: urban refuges. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 80, 108–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baee.2024.09.002>.
- Biella, P., Borghesan, S., Colombo, B., Galimberti, A., Guzzetti, L., Maggioni, D., Pioltelli, E., Ramazzotti, F., Ranalli, R., Tommasi, N., Labra, M., 2025. Lawn management promoting tall herbs, flowering species and urban park attributes enhance insect biodiversity in urban green areas. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 104, 128650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128650>.
- Blüthgen, N., Menzel, F., Blüthgen, N., 2006. Measuring specialization in species interaction networks. *BMC Ecol.* 14, 6–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6785-6-9>.

- Brown, J., Threlfall, C.G., Harrison, L., Baumann, J., Williams, N.S.G., 2024. Rapid responses of bees and butterflies but not birds to targeted urban road verge habitat enhancements. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 61 (6), 1312–1322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14648>.
- Buchholz, S., Egerer, M.H., 2020. Functional ecology of wild bees in cities: towards a better understanding of trait-urbanization relationships. *Biodivers. Conserv.* 29 (9–10), 2779–2801. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-020-02003-8>.
- Buchholz, S., Gathof, A.K., Grossmann, A.J., Kowarik, I., Fischer, L.K., 2020. Wild bees in urban grasslands: urbanisation, functional diversity and species traits. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 196, 103731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2019.103731>.
- Cappellari, A., Marini, L., 2021. Improving insect conservation across heterogeneous landscapes using species-habitat networks. *PeerJ* 9, e10563. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.10563>.
- Casanelles-Abella, J., Müller, S., Keller, A., Aleixo, C., Alós Orti, M., Chiron, F., Deguines, N., Hallikma, T., Laanisto, L., Pinho, P., Samson, R., Tryjanowski, P., Van Mensel, A., Pellissier, L., Moretti, M., 2022. How wild bees find a way in European cities: pollen metabarcoding unravels multiple feeding strategies and their effects on distribution patterns in four wild bee species. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 59 (2), 457–470. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14063>.
- Cloutier, S., Mendes, P., Cimon-Morin, J., Pellerin, S., Fournier, V., Poulin, M., 2024. Assessing the contribution of lawns and semi-natural meadows to bee, wasp, and flower fly communities across different landscapes. *Urban Ecosyst.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-024-01516-2>.
- Daniels, B., Jedamski, J., Ottermann, R., Ross-Nickoll, M., 2020. A “plan bee” for cities: pollinator diversity and plant-pollinator interactions in urban green spaces. *PLoS One* 15 (7), e0235492. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235492>.
- Dargas, J.H.F., Chaves, S.R., Fischer, E., 2016. Pollination of lark daisy on roadsides declines as traffic speed increases along an Amazonian highway. *Plant Biol.* 18 (3), 542–544. <https://doi.org/10.1111/plb.12437>.
- Dormann, C.F., Strauss, R., 2014. A method for detecting modules in quantitative bipartite networks. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 5 (1), 90–98. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12139>.
- Dong, Z., Bladon, A.J., Jaworski, C.C., Pywell, R.F., Woodcock, B.A., Meek, W.R., Nuttall, P., Dicks, L.V., 2025. Species-habitat networks reveal conservation implications that other community analyses do not detect. *Ecol. Appl.* 35 (1), e3073. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.3073>.
- Dormann, C.F., Gruber, B., Fründ, J., 2008a. *Introducing the Bipartite Package: Analysing Ecological Networks*, vol. 8.
- Dormann, C.F., Gruber, B., Frund, J., 2008b. Introducing the bipartite package: analysing ecological networks. *R News* 8 (2), 8–11. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000265935>.
- Dunne, J.A., Williams, R.J., Martinez, N.D., 2002. Network structure and biodiversity loss in food webs: robustness increases with connectance. *Ecol. Lett.* 5 (4), 558–567. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.2002.00354.x>.
- Dunne, J.A., Williams, R.J., Martinez, N.D., 2004. Network structure and robustness of marine food webs. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 273, 291–302. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps273291>.
- Dylewski, L., Maćkowiak, L., Banaszak-Cibicka, W., 2019. Are all urban green spaces a favourable habitat for pollinator communities? Bees, butterflies and hoverflies in different urban green areas. *Ecol. Entomol.* 44 (5), 678–689. <https://doi.org/10.1111/een.12744>.
- Felderhoff, J., Gathof, A.K., Buchholz, S., Egerer, M., 2023. Vegetation complexity and nesting resource availability predict bee diversity and functional traits in community gardens. *Ecol. Appl.* 33 (2), e2759. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2759>.
- Fenoglio, M.S., Rossetti, M.R., Videla, M., 2020. Negative effects of urbanization on terrestrial arthropod communities: a meta-analysis. *Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.* 29 (8), 1412–1429. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13107>.
- Ferrari, A., Polidori, C., 2022. How city traits affect taxonomic and functional diversity of urban wild bee communities: insights from a worldwide analysis. *Apidologie* 53 (4), 46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13592-022-00950-5>.
- Ferrari, A., Polidori, C., Trisoglio, C.F., Bonasoro, F., 2024. Increasing road cover in urban areas is associated with greater midgut histological damage in a primitively eusocial bee. *Insect. Soc.* 71 (3), 331–341. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-024-00980-5>.
- Fournier, B., Frey, D., Moretti, M., 2020. The origin of urban communities: from the regional species pool to community assemblages in city. *J. Biogeogr.* 47 (3), 615–629. <https://doi.org/10.1111/JBI.13772>.
- Fox, J., Weisberg, S., Bates, D., Firth, D., Friendly, M., Gor, G., Graves, S., Heiberger, R., Labossiere, R., Mon, G., Nilsson, H., Ogle, D., Ripley, B., Zeileis, A., 2012. *The Car Package*. R, pp. 1–147.
- Gathof, A.K., Grossmann, A.J., Herrmann, J., Buchholz, S., 2022. Who can pass the urban filter? A multi-taxon approach to disentangle pollinator trait–environmental relationships. *Oecologia* 2022 (1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00442-022-05174-Z>.
- Geppert, C., Cappellari, A., Corcos, D., Caruso, V., Cerretti, P., Mei, M., Marini, L., 2022. Temperature and not landscape composition shapes wild bee communities in an urban environment. *Insect Conserv. Divers.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12602>.
- Girling, R.D., Lusebrink, I., Farthing, E., Newman, T.A., Poppy, G.M., 2013. Diesel exhaust rapidly degrades floral odours used by honeybees. *Sci. Rep.* 3 (1), 2779. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep02779>.
- Greenleaf, S.S., Williams, N.M., Winfree, R., Kremen, C., 2007. Bee foraging ranges and their relationship to body size. *Oecologia* 153 (3), 589–596. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-007-0752-9>.
- Halbritter, D.A., Daniels, J.C., Whitaker, D.C., Huang, L., 2015. Reducing mowing frequency increases floral resource and butterfly (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea and Papilionoidea) abundance in managed roadside margins. *Fla. Entomol.* 98 (4), 1081–1092. <https://doi.org/10.1653/024.098.0412>.
- Hemmings, K., Elton, R., Grange, I., 2022. No-mow amenity grassland case study: phenology of floral abundance and nectar resource. *Ecol. Solut. Evid.* 3 (4), e12179. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12179>.
- Jakobsson, S., Bernes, C., Bullock, J.M., Verheyen, K., Lindborg, R., 2018. How does roadside vegetation management affect the diversity of vascular plants and invertebrates? A systematic review. *Environ. Evid.* 7 (1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-018-0129-z>.
- Lami, F., Bartomeus, I., Nardi, D., Beduschi, T., Boscutti, F., Pantini, P., Santoemma, G., Scherber, C., Tschamtké, T., Marini, L., 2021. Species-habitat networks elucidate landscape effects on habitat specialisation of natural enemies and pollinators. *Ecol. Lett.* 24 (2), 288–297. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13642>.
- Lanner, J., Kratschmer, S., Petrović, B., Gaulhofer, F., Meimberg, H., Pachinger, B., 2020. City dwelling wild bees: how communal gardens promote species richness. *Urban Ecosyst.* 23 (2), 271–288. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-019-00902-5>.
- Lerman, S.B., Contosta, A.R., Milam, J., Bang, C., 2018. To mow or to mow less: lawn mowing frequency affects bee abundance and diversity in suburban yards. *Biol. Conserv.* 221, 160–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2018.01.025>.
- Li, G., Fang, C., Li, Y., Wang, Z., Sun, S., He, S., Qi, W., Bao, C., Ma, H., Fan, Y., Feng, Y., Liu, X., 2022. Global impacts of future urban expansion on terrestrial vertebrate diversity. *Nat. Commun.* 13 (1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29324-2>.
- Liang, H., He, Y.-D., Theodorou, P., Yang, C.-F., 2023. The effects of urbanization on pollinators and pollination: a meta-analysis. *Ecol. Lett.* 26 (9), 1629–1642. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.14277>.
- Marini, L., Bartomeus, I., Rader, R., Lami, F., 2019. Species-habitat networks: a tool to improve landscape management for conservation. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 56 (4), 923–928. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13337>.
- McCune, F., Normandin, É., Gervais, A., Mazerolle, M.J., Fournier, V., 2023. Syrphid fly response to urban heat islands varies with functional traits. *J. Insect Conserv.* 27 (5), 693–705. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-023-00490-y>.
- McFrederick, Q.S., LeBuhn, G., 2006. Are urban parks refuges for bumble bees *Bombus* spp. (Hymenoptera: Apidae)? *Biol. Conserv.* 129 (3), 372–382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.11.004>.
- Meinzen, T.C., Burklee, L.A., Debinski, D.M., 2024. Roadside habitat: boon or bane for pollinating insects? *BioScience* 74 (1), 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biad111>.
- Memmott, J., Waser, N.M., Price, M.V., 2004. Tolerance of pollination networks to species extinctions. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. B Biol. Sci.* 271 (1557), 2605–2611. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2004.2909>.
- Muratet, A., Fontaine, B., 2015. Contrasting impacts of pesticides on butterflies and bumblebees in private gardens in France. *Biol. Conserv.* 182, 148–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.11.045>.
- Noordijk, J., Delille, K., Schaffers, A.P., Sýkora, K.V., 2009. Optimizing grassland management for flower-visiting insects in roadside verges. *Biol. Conserv.* 142 (10), 2097–2103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2009.04.009>.
- Olesen, J.M., Bascompte, J., Dupont, Y.L., Jordano, P., 2007. The modularity of pollination networks. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 104 (50), 19891–19896. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0706375104>.
- Pereira, F.W., Carneiro, L., Gonçalves, R.B., 2021. More losses than gains in ground-nesting bees over 60 years of urbanization. *Urban Ecosyst.* 24 (2), 233–242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-020-01030-1>.
- Phillips, B.B., Wallace, C., Roberts, B.R., Whitehouse, A.T., Gaston, K.J., Bullock, J.M., Dicks, L.V., Osborne, J.L., 2020. Enhancing road verges to aid pollinator conservation: a review. *Biol. Conserv.* 250, 108687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108687>.
- Pinheiro, J., Bates, D., R Core Team, 2017. *nlme: Linear and Nonlinear Mixed Effects Models* (p. 3.1-168) [Data set]. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.nlme>.
- Proske, A., Lokatis, S., Rolf, J., 2022. Impact of mowing frequency on arthropod abundance and diversity in urban habitats: a meta-analysis. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 76, 127714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2022.127714>.
- R Core Team, 2017. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing.
- Remmers, R., Frantzeskaki, N., 2024. Bees in the city: findings from a scoping review and recommendations for urban planning. *Ambio*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-024-02028-1>.
- Rivest, S.A., Kharouba, H.M., 2024. Taxonomic and functional homogenization of butterfly communities along an urban gradient. *Insect Conserv. Divers.* 17 (2), 273–286. <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12729>.
- Shwartz, A., Muratet, A., Simon, L., Julliard, R., 2013. Local and management variables outweigh landscape effects in enhancing the diversity of different taxa in a big metropolis. *Biol. Conserv.* 157, 285–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.09.009>.
- Süle, G., Kovács-Hostyánszki, A., Sárosipataki, M., Kelemen, T.I., Halassy, G., Horváth, A., Demeter, I., Báldi, A., Szigeti, V., 2023. First steps of pollinator-promoting interventions in Eastern European urban areas – positive outcomes, challenges, and recommendations. *Urban Ecosyst.* 26 (6), 1783–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-023-01420-1>.
- Theodorou, P., Radzevičiūtė, R., Lentendu, G., Kahnt, B., Husemann, M., Bleidorn, C., Settele, J., Schweiger, O., Grosse, I., Wubet, T., Murray, T.E., Paxton, R.J., 2020. Urban areas as hotspots for bees and pollination but not a panacea for all insects. *Nat. Commun.* 11 (1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-14496-6>.
- Threlfall, C.G., Walker, K., Williams, N.S.G., Hahs, A.K., Mata, L., Stork, N., Livesley, S.J., 2015. The conservation value of urban green space habitats for Australian native bee communities. *Biol. Conserv.* 187, 240–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2015.05.003>.

- Tonietto, R., Fant, J., Ascher, J., Ellis, K., Larkin, D., 2011. A comparison of bee communities of Chicago green roofs, parks and prairies. *Landscape Urban Plan.* 103 (1), 102–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2011.07.004>.
- Valtonen, A., Saarinen, K., Jantunen, J., 2006. Effect of different mowing regimes on butterflies and diurnal moths on road verges. *Anim. Biodivers. Conserv.* 29 (2), 133–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2004.12.012>.
- Wilson, C.J., Jamieson, M.A., 2019. The effects of urbanization on bee communities depends on floral resource availability and bee functional traits. *PLoS One* 14 (12), e0225852. <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0225852>.